

VIBRATION AND DAMPING ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES BY USING A NEW RECTANGULAR PLATE FINITE ELEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, a rectangular plate bending element based on a Higher order Shear Deformation Theory is developed. The element has 4 nodes and 20 degrees of freedom. The transverse displacement is interpolated by using an optimized interpolation function. A damped element is introduced to the finite element model. The proposed FEM is used to calculate eigenfrequencies and modal damping of composite plates with various boundary conditions and different thicknesses. The results show that the present FEM gives excellent results for both thick and thin plates. The proposed finite element model does not lock in the thin plate situation and does not contain any spurious vibration mode.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite laminates have relatively low transverse shear stiffness as compared to the inplane stiffness and, therefore, the effect of the transverse shear deformation should be considered. Many works on finite element modelling of composite laminates have been based on the first or higher order shear deformation theories. FE model based on the first order shear deformation theory (FSDT) has the advantage of requiring only C^0 -continuity of all primary variables. However, its direct application to thin plate situation often induces "shear locking" behaviour. The reduced and selective integration may be used to avoid the shear locking, but spurious vibration modes might occur^[1]. This is disadvantageous to the inverse analysis of vibration of structure in which modal parameters between analysis and experiment need to be matched. The mixed finite element models^[2] do not combine well with the more numerous displacement-based elements which are widely used in commercial codes. In recent years, several displacement finite element models^[3,4] based on higher order theories have been developed. However, the accuracy and efficiency of these methods need to be improved. The objective of this paper is to develop a finite element model which can overcome "shear locking", avoid spurious modes, converge as rapidly as possible, and provide a good basis for the inverse analysis of vibration of composite laminates.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND DISPLACEMENT FIELD

Consider an orthotropic rectangular plate with thickness h , as shown in Fig.1. In order to derive the displacement for this plate, a shear deformation theory, called Component Theory which was

developed by Panc [5], is used. The stresses from the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis are taken as a first approximation. The transverse shearing stresses and further, the transverse shearing strains, may be obtained by using the conditions of equilibrium of the 3-dimensional elastic body. The x-y plane displacements u and v may be expressed by transverse displacement w . then, the displacement field for finite element analysis may be derived as

$$\mathbf{u} = -z\mathbf{w}_{,x} + \varphi_x f(z) \quad \mathbf{v} = -z\mathbf{w}_{,y} + \varphi_y f(z) \quad \mathbf{w} = w(x,y) \quad (1)$$

with, $f(z) = z[1 - (4/3)(z/h)^2]$, $(,)$ denotes the derivative with respect the quantity preceding it.

Fig.1 Laminate geometry and fibre orientation

The strain components may be written as

$$\epsilon_x = -z w_{,xx} + f(z) \varphi_{x,x} \quad (2)$$

$$\epsilon_y = -z w_{,yy} + f(z) \varphi_{y,y} \quad (3)$$

$$\epsilon_{xy} = -2z w_{,xy} + f(z) (\varphi_{x,y} + \varphi_{y,x}) \quad (4)$$

$$\epsilon_{xz} = f(z) \varphi_x \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_{yz} = f(z) \varphi_y \quad (6)$$

where, φ_x and φ_y may be considered as shearing angles. It can be seen from Eq.(5) and Eq.(6) that the transverse shear strains ϵ_{xz} and ϵ_{yz} are independent from the transverse displacement w , which is convenient to the derivation of FE formulation. Especially, as the plate becomes thin, φ_x and φ_y will become very small and the present displacement field will be identical with the one given by the classical plate theory. Therefore, it would not induce the "shear lock" in the thin plate situation due to the selection of interpolation functions.

3 FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

A Higher order Rectangular Plate Element, called HRPE, is developed based on the above displacement field. The element has 4 nodes and each node has 5 degrees of freedom ($w, w_x, w_y, \varphi_x, \varphi_y$). The element is shown in Fig.2.

Fig.2 Rectangular plate element

3.1 Interpolation functions

The transverse displacement is interpolated by using an optimal interpolation function S_j as proposed in Ref.[6], whereas the two additional rotations are interpolated by using the linear Lagrange interpolation function N_j :

$$w = \sum_{j=1}^{12} S_j \delta_j \quad \varphi_x = \sum_{j=1}^4 N_j \delta_{xj} \quad \varphi_y = \sum_{j=1}^4 N_j \delta_{yj} \quad (7)$$

with

$$[S]^T = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(\xi)h_1(\eta,r) + f_1(\eta)h_1(\xi,r) - h_1(\eta,r)h_1(\xi,r) \\ g(\eta)h_1(\xi,p)b \\ -g(\xi)h_1(\eta,q)a \\ \\ f_1(1-\xi)h_1(\eta,r) + f_1(\eta)h_1(1-\xi,r) - h_1(\eta,r)h_1(1-\xi,r) \\ g(\eta)h_1(1-\xi,p)b \\ g(1-\xi)h_1(\eta,q)a \\ \\ f_1(1-\xi)h_1(1-\eta,r) + f_1(1-\eta)h_1(1-\xi,r) - h_1(1-\eta,r)h_1(1-\xi,r) \\ -g(1-\eta)h_1(1-\xi,p)b \\ g(1-\xi)h_1(1-\eta,q)a \\ \\ f_1(\xi)h_1(1-\eta,r) + f_1(1-\eta)h_1(\xi,r) - h_1(1-\eta,r)h_1(\xi,r) \\ -g(1-\eta)h_1(\xi,p)b \\ -g(\xi)h_1(1-\eta,q)a \end{bmatrix}$$

where $\xi=x/a$, $\eta=y/b$, p , q and r are variable parameters which can be determined from the convergence requirements. The best results can be obtained when $p=q=1$ and $r=2^{[6]}$. f_1 , g and h_1 are the following functions

$$f_1(t) = (1-t)^2(1+2t), \quad g(t) = t(1-t)^2, \quad h_1(t,s) = (1-t)(1+st/2 - s^2 t^2)$$

where, t and s are independent variables. Eq.(7) may be written in matrix form:

$$\{\bar{w}\} = [\bar{N}]\{\bar{\delta}\} \quad (8)$$

where, $\{\bar{w}\} = \{w \ \varphi_x \ \varphi_y\}^T$, $\{\bar{\delta}\} = \{\delta_1 \ \delta_2 \ \dots \ \delta_{12} \ \delta_{x1} \ \delta_{y1} \ \dots \ \delta_{x4} \ \delta_{y4}\}$ and

$$[\bar{N}] = \begin{bmatrix} [S] & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & N_1 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & N_4 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & N_1 & 0 & N_2 & 0 & N_3 & 0 & N_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

3.2 Element Stiffness Matrix

From Eq.(2)~(6), we have,

$$\{\epsilon\} = [T(z)]\{\epsilon_g\} \quad (9)$$

where, $\{\epsilon_g\}$ is the generalized strain vector.

$$\{\epsilon_g\} = [w_{,xx} \ w_{,yy} \ 2w_{,xy} \ \varphi_{,x,x} \ \varphi_{,y,y} \ (\varphi_{,x,y} + \varphi_{,y,x}) \ \varphi_x \ \varphi_y]^T$$

and

$$[T(z)] = \begin{bmatrix} -z & 0 & 0 & f(z) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -z & 0 & 0 & f(z) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -z & 0 & 0 & f(z) & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f'(z) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f'(z) \end{bmatrix}$$

By using Eq.(9) and the constitutive relation in Appendix, the total strain energy is

$$U = \int \{\epsilon_g\}^T [D] \{\epsilon_g\} dx dy \quad (10)$$

where, the mean elasticity matrix of each element, [D], is given by

$$[D] = \sum_1^n \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} [T(z)]^T [Q] [T(z)] dz \quad (11)$$

In Eq.(11), n is the number of laminae, h_{k-1} and h_k are the lower and upper co-ordinates of the k^{th} layer.

Based on Eq.(8), the generalized strain vector may be expressed by nodal displacement

$$\{\epsilon_g\} = [B]\{\bar{\delta}\} \quad (12)$$

Element stiffness matrix is

$$[K]_e = \int [B]^T [D] [B] dx dy \quad (13)$$

3.3 Element Mass Matrix

The consistent mass matrix is used:

$$[M]_e = \int [\bar{N}]^T [m] \bar{N} dx dy \quad (14)$$

where,

$$[m] = \begin{bmatrix} c_1 I_{1,12 \times 12} & 0 \\ 0 & c_2 I_{2,8 \times 8} \end{bmatrix}$$

with

$$(c_1, c_2) = \sum_1^n \int_{h_{k-1}}^{h_k} \rho^i(1, z^2) dz$$

ρ^i is the mass density of the i th layer. I_1 and I_2 are unit matrices

3.4 Element Damping Matrix

In this investigation, the damping element model given in Ref.[7] is used. The element damping matrix is

$$[C]_e = \int [B]^T [D_d] [B] dx dy \quad (15)$$

where, $[D_d] = [\phi][Q]$, and $[\phi] = \text{diag}(\phi_i)$. ϕ_i ($i=1,5$) is the specific damping capacity.

3.5 Calculation of Natural Frequency and Damping

Suppose that the damping is hysteretic, i.e, it is independent of vibration frequency. For free vibration, the characteristic equation of the plate is

$$([K] + i[C] - \omega_j^2 [M]) \{\delta\}_j = 0 \quad (16)$$

Solving Eq.(16), the complex variable ω^2 is obtained

$$\omega_j^2 = \omega_{dj}^2 (1 + i\eta_j) \quad (17)$$

The j th natural frequency of the structure is $f_j = \omega_{dj} / 2\pi$. and η_j is the j th modal damping.

4 NUMERICAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To demonstrate the utility of the present finite element model, various examples have been considered. In all the numerical examples, the bending and shearing energy and inertia terms are exactly integrated by using 4x4 Gauss points. For the purpose of comparison, some of the evaluations are conducted on sample problems for which either exact solution or finite element results are available in the open literature. The numerical tests on the present FE model include the following aspects: the application to thin and thick plates and angle-ply laminates with simply supported or free boundary conditions, the convergency of the results, the ability of predicting damping and the validity of the optimal interpolation function. The material parameters used in calculation are listed in Table 1. All plates are discretized with 6x6 elements except for plate 3 (4x8 elements). The calculated results are presented in Table 2 to Table 5.

Table 1. Material parameters

Plate	E_1 (Gpa)	E_2 (Gpa)	G_{12} (Gpa)	G_{13} (Gpa)	G_{23} (Gpa)	ν_{12}	$\rho(\text{kgm}^{-3})$
1	1	1	1/2.6	1/2.6	1/2.6	0.3	1
2	40	1	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.25	1
3	131.7	9.86	4.21	4.21	4.21	0.28	1600
4	172.7	7.20	3.76	3.76	3.76	0.3	1566

Table 2. Comparison of the first five natural frequencies, $\lambda = \omega h(\rho/G_{12})^{1/2}$ of simply supported isotropic square plate (plate 1, L/h=10)

(m,n)	Present FEM	3D elasticity	Mindlin	Ref.[8]	Ref.[3]	CPT
(1,1)	0.0933(0.11)	0.0932	0.0930	0.0930(0.21)	0.0929(0.32)	0.963
(2,1)	0.2239(0.58)	0.2226	0.2218	0.2219(0.18)	0.2216(0.44)	0.2408
(2,2)	0.3422(0.03)	0.3421	0.3402	0.3388(0.96)	0.3379(1.22)	0.3853
(3,1)	0.4231(1.44)	0.4171	0.4144	0.4195(0.58)	0.4184(0.31)	0.4816
(3,2)	0.5252(0.25)	0.5239	0.5197	0.5158(1.55)	0.5152(1.66)	0.6261
(3,3)	0.6869(0.29)	0.6889	0.6821	0.6577(4.53)	0.6941(0.75)	0.8686
DOFs	165			175	350	

Note: 1) Values in parentheses give percentage errors with respect to the 3D elasticity solution
 2) DOFs mean the degrees of freedom of the plate after introducing displacement boundary condition
 3) (m,n) indicate a mode with m and n half-waves in the X- and Y- directions, respectively

Table 3. Effect of length to thickness ratio (L/h) on the dimensionless fundamental frequencies $\lambda = \omega(L^2/h)(\rho/E_2)^{1/2}$ of simply supported cross-ply ($0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}$) square plate. (plate 2)

L/h	5	10	20	50	100
Present FEM	10.657(-0.23)	15.054(-0.1)	17.526(-0.62)	18.537(-0.71)	18.700(-0.72)
Analysis ^[9]	10.682	15.069	17.636	18.670	18.835
Ref.[10]	11.770(10.2)	15.940(5.78)	17.993(2.02)	18.738(0.36)	18.852(0.09)
CPT	18.215	18.652	18.767	18.799	18.804

Note: Values in parentheses is percentage errors with respect to the analytical solution of Ref.[9].

Table 4. Comparison of natural frequencies $\lambda = \omega(L^2/h)(\rho/E_2)^{1/2}$ of completely free angle-ply $[(-45^{\circ}/+45^{\circ})_8]_{\text{symmetric}}$ plate. (plate 3, H/L=2, L/h=100)

Mode No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Analysis ^[11]	8.58	23.38	29.19	45.79	48.68	66.74	68.02	78.81
Present	8.60	23.38	29.44	46.10	48.80	67.57	68.14	79.27
Error(%)	0.23	0.00	0.86	0.68	0.25	1.24	0.18	0.58

Table 5. Comparison of natural frequencies (Hz) and damping of completely free 8-layer (all 0°) glass fibre reinforced plate (plate 4, H=L=178, h=1.58mm, $\phi_1=0.45\%$, $\phi_2=4.22\%$, $\phi_3=\phi_4=\phi_5=7.05\%$)

Mode	Natural frequency			Modal damping		
	Present FEM	Experiment Ref.[7]	Ref.[7] FEM	Present FEM(%)	Experiment Ref.[7](%)	Ref.[7] FEM(%)
1	81.98	81.5	83.57	6.89	7.0	6.76
2	109.96	107.4	118.42	4.22	4.9	4.28
3	202.23	196.6	207.79	5.98	5.4	5.89
4	303.66	295.5	329.41	4.22	4.7	4.13
5	400.15	382.5	419.83	5.11	4.8	5.11
6	538.46	531.0	546.93			

As seen from the above results, the present FE model gives satisfactory results on both natural frequency and damping for thin and thick plates, isotropic plates and angle-ply laminates under simply supported or free boundary conditions. The discrepancies in natural frequencies are less than 2% compared to the exact solution. The errors of damping between prediction and experiment are around 10%. These results are reasonable because the measurement errors of damping usually are large (maybe 5%~ 20%). For most of the cases, the present method gives more accurate predictions when compared with other FE models. The present FE results approach to those of classical plate theory as the plates become thin. Compared with C⁰ continuous finite element models (based on FSDT or HSDT), the present method does not need to use reduced or selective integration to avoid "shear lock". Therefore, any spurious vibration mode would not be introduced. This is advantageous to the inverse analysis of vibration of structures because modal parameters between analysis and experiment need to be matched in some cases.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper a new higher order rectangular plate element (HRPE) is developed based on a shear deformation theory. Various numerical tests have been performed, demonstrating that the HRPE is reliable and efficient for both thin and thick composite laminates in vibration analysis. In particular, the present FE model does not lock in the thin plate situation and does not contain any spurious vibration modes. The use of the optimal interpolation function makes the present method yield sufficiently accurate results by using a relatively small number of degrees of freedom.

The present method is limited to vibration analysis of symmetrical laminated plates. It is, however, not difficult to extend it to general cases by adding in-plane displacement into the present FE model.

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APPENDIX: CONSTITUTIVE EQUATIONS

For a plate of constant thickness which is composed of thin layers of orthotropic material, under the assumption that each layer possesses a plane of elastic symmetry parallel to the x-y plane, the relationship between stress $\{\sigma\}$ and $\{\epsilon\}$ for a layer can be written as:

$$\{\sigma\} = [\bar{Q}]\{\epsilon\}$$

and

$$[\bar{Q}] = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ Q_{21} & Q_{22} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{33} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{44} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & Q_{55} \end{bmatrix}$$

where, Q_{ij} are the plane stress reduced elastic constants in the material axis of the layer. The relationship between Q_{ij} and engineering elastic constants is:

$$Q_{11} = E_1 / \mu, \quad Q_{12} = \nu_{12} E_2 / \mu, \quad Q_{22} = E_2 / \mu, \quad Q_{33} = G_{12}, \quad Q_{44} = G_{13}, \quad Q_{55} = G_{23}, \quad \mu = 1 - \nu_{12} \nu_{21}$$

The transformed stress-strain relation for a layer is:

$$\{\sigma\} = [Q]\{\epsilon\}$$

$$[Q] = [R]^T [\bar{Q}] [R]$$

where, the transformation matrix $[R]$ is

$$[R] = \begin{bmatrix} m^2 & n^2 & mn & 0 & 0 \\ n^2 & m^2 & -mn & 0 & 0 \\ -2mn & 2mn & m^2 - n^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m & -n \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & n & m \end{bmatrix}$$

and $m = \cos\theta$, $n = \sin\theta$. θ is the angle between the positive direction of x and the fibre.

NEW MATERIALS AND SMART STRUCTURES
